

World Education Connect

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842

ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

Vol. IV Issue VIII, August 2024

Monthly Issue

International Circulation

Pinagpala
PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 3269

DTI Business Reg. No. 3034433

TIN 293-150-678/ Business Permit No. 8183

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Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue VIII (August 2024), pp.1-2, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

LEARNERS' LEARNING STYLES: BASIS FOR PROVIDING CLASSROOM LEARNING ACTIVITIES TO ACHIEVE EFFECTIVE LEARNING

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Teacher should spread his presence far outside of the classroom setting who create a positive learning environment to learners for him to accommodate the academic needs of learners in learning. A teacher of the new normal should emphasize more on the learning activities that address learners' individual differences and learning styles to achieve effective learning that leads to higher academic performance of the learners in the school. An effective teacher's view of his learners should be holistic, compassionate, and seeks what works better in the classroom in developing learners' potentials.

The most effective and efficient teacher of today is the one who can execute different best practices that provide meaningful learnings for all learners, because this teacher knows how to motivate learners' learning by combining intellectual teaching techniques and strategies to meet the academic needs of different learners. A teacher also develops and improves the skills of the learners that produce the best learning outcomes. Teacher who is a facilitator of learning do not act as the keeper of knowledge but as the source and the imparter of knowledge who pass on learnings to learners.

There are learners who do better in some classes than others, but then, it may depend on the individual learning styles and differences of the learners. Their learning styles have high impact on how they comprehend information and how they solve problems. Learners learn most based on their own learning styles. These learning styles may be visual, auditory, or kinaesthetic. Teachers who vary their instructional teaching techniques and methods to address all the major learning styles and mark-up the importance of learner's learning styles tend to have greater success in reaching all learners' needs and may help their learners from reaching their maximum possible learning potentials.

Many teachers know that each learner has individual differences and have different learning styles in learning, but only few teachers execute differentiated instructions, use varied learning activities, and heterogeneous tasks that may cater their learners' learning. Every learner has a mix of learning styles therefore, by recognizing and understanding their different learning styles, the teacher can use techniques better suited to them. This improves the speed and quality of their learnings.

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According to Dunn and Dunn Learning Styles Model, learners tend to perform patterns in the way they prefer to deal with new and challenging information and ideas. Learners are more assertive and successful when they solve difficult tasks by means of their strengths and by means of their forte. The Dunn and Dunn Learning Style Model show a range of varied instructions that demonstrated positive influence to the achievements of every learner from young age to adulthood. It involves learners' learning experiences in terms of environmental, emotional, sociological, physiological, and psychological.

Therefore, schools and teachers should have collaborative efforts to modify and enhance different learning activities that cater individual learners' learning styles and focus upon developing learners' independence in learning and problem solving. Learners should also be given challenging tasks that suit to their learning styles which enhance their critical-thinking and problem-solving skills which in turn leads to better academic outcomes.

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.13268268

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